

Interview with Marc Prensky* on “New Roles for (Digital) Natives and Immigrants – Can We Use the Increasing Differences to Our Advantage?”

Marc Prensky ile “(Dijital) Yerliler ve Göçmenler için Yeni Roller - Artan Farklılıkları Avantajımız Olarak Kullanabilir miyiz?” Üzerine Söyleşi

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Anahtar Kelimeler

Marc Prensky,
Dijital Yerliler,
Dijital göçmenler,
Dijitalleşme,
Eğitim

Öz

Teorik ve pratik boyutları ile güncel gelişmeleri ve yeni okuryazarlık arayışlarını ihmal etmeden araştırma ve eğitimi birlikte ele almayı hedefleyen bir akademik süreli yayın olan Medya Okuryazarlığı Araştırmaları Dergisi, akademisyenler ve araştırmacıların yanında eğitimciler, ebeveynler ile medya ve iletişim profesyonellerinin de deneyim ve birikimlerini buluşturan bir platform olma hedefiyle çalışmalarını yürütmektedir. Bu amaçla düzenlenen Müktesebat Toplantıları üst başlıklı toplantı dizilerinde Tez ve Makale Sunumları, Yöntem Konuşmaları, Bir Kitap Bir Yazar, Saha Araştırmaları Deneyimi, Dijital Deneyimler vb. alt başlıklardaki programlarla akademik ve entelektüel birikim tartışılmakta ve bu vesile ile yeni çalışmalara, araştırmalara ilham kaynağı oluşturacak bir ortamın oluşmasını hedeflemektedir.

Marc Prensky'nin 2001 yılında “dijital yerliler ve dijital göçmenler” kavramlarını tartışarak sunduğu iki makalesini¹ ilk defa Türkçeye kazandırmanın yanında 20 yıllık aranın ardından konuyu yeniden almasına ilişkin bir söyleşi gerçekleştirdik. Müktesebat Toplantıları kapsamında “New Roles for (Digital) Natives and Immigrants – Can We Use the Increasing Differences to Our Advantage?” başlığı ile çevrimiçi ortamda gerçekleştirdiğimiz söyleşinin deşifre edilmiş metnine orijinal haliyle dergimizin bu sayısında yer veriyoruz.”

Keywords

Marc Prensky,
Digital Native,
Digital Immigrants,
Digitalization,
Education

Abstract

The Journal of Media Literacy Studies aims to serve as a forum for the production and exchange of knowledge and ideas concerning new developments in media literacy research and education. Beyond functioning solely as an academic journal, it seeks to engage in discussions about existing academic knowledge and serve as a source of inspiration for new studies. From this perspective, Müktesebat Toplantıları is organized as a series of meetings where various academic studies, intellectual knowledge, and experiences are presented, shared, and discussed under the umbrella of the Journal of Media Literacy Studies. We have various sub-titles such as “Thesis Presentation, Method Talks, One Article, One Author, One Book, One Author, Research Experience, Digital Experiences.”

In this context, we are launching a new series of Müktesebat Toplantıları with the subtitle Media Literacy Talks. The first speaker of the Media Literacy Talks will be Marc Prensky, who conceptualized digital immigrants and digital natives and addressed the issue with two articles in 2001. The title of the talk is “New Roles for (Digital) Natives and Immigrants-Can We Use the Increasing Differences to Our Advantage?” Moderated by Dr. Gülden Demir, we talked with Prensky about the background of the concept of digital natives and digital immigrants, how they are different, and his suggestions for parents, educators, and teachers to use increasing significant differences to their advantage.

* The interview with Marc Prensky was conducted online on June 21, 2023. The interview recording can be accessed on the Media Literacy Journal YouTube channel.

¹ Bkz. Marc Prensky, “Dijital Yerliler, Dijital Göçmenler -1” çev. Gülden Demir, *Medya Okuryazarlığı Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2023, 2, s. 47-51 <https://medyaokuryazari.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/5-Dijital-Yerliler-Dijital-Gocmenler.pdf> ve Marc Prensky, “Dijital Yerliler, Dijital Göçmenler -2 ve Gerçekten Farklı Düşünüyorlar mı?” çev. Gülden Demir, *Medya Okuryazarlığı Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2023, 3, s.69-78

Gülден Demir: Hello and welcome to the first session of Media Literacy Talks held under the umbrella of The Journal of Media Literacy Studies. Thank you for being with us and joining us! Today we have a special guest: Marc Prensky.

Marc is the founder and executive director of the global feature of Education Foundation and Institute and the creator of the *Two Billion Kids Project*. He is an internationally acclaimed keynote speaker, author, visionary, and generator of new ideas, offering audiences better and alternative ways for succeeding in the fast-changing 21st century. He speaks on a variety of topics related to young people and generational change, and Marc has spoken in almost 50 countries on six continents. So, he is literally everywhere in the world. He has published 10 books and written over 200 essays and articles. His writings have been translated into many languages, including Turkish. Marc’s book *Education to Better Their World’: Unleashing the Power of 21st Century Kids* won a Foreword INDIES Book of the Year Award Gold Prize. His latest book is *Empowered! Re-Framing ‘Growing Up’ For A New Age*.

Marc Prensky is best known for coining the terms *digital natives* and *digital immigrants*. They are both in the Oxford Dictionary now, and you can read the Turkish translation of the article titled *Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants* in the second issue of our journal, the Journal of Media Literacy Studies. In this issue, we’re presenting the Turkish translation of the second article by Marc Prensky: *Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants-Part 2: Do They Really Think Differently?* His career as a teacher includes teaching at all levels, and he has been a professional musician and has acted on Broadway. We’re going to talk to him today.

Hello Marc, welcome to our session. I want to start with actually how you got started. You have a background in science; then next move was teaching at all levels and then becoming founder of a video game development company. Can you tell us about this journey and the background of the concepts of ‘digital natives’ and ‘digital immigrants’ and how they are different?

Marc Prensky: Well, let me see if I can resume my journey as quickly as possible because it has a lot of varied paths. I grew up, and I’m perhaps older than I look. I grew up in the period right when the Soviet Union launched Sputnik, which was the first satellite in the world, and that put a huge pressure on the world and on my country to catch up in science. Somehow, we got the idea that we were behind. So, I was one of the first groups that was pushed hard into what’s now called STEM (science, technology, engineering, and math), and I went through that for many years. I liked it, and I did well in it, but I finally decided it was not going to be my profession. So, when I was in university, when I was in college, I realized that I was much more interested in more general things in the world. I switched my major from chemistry to French. Then, I went and spent some time in France, and I loved Europe. I had a very good time there. I came back, and I had to have a job. The job that was available for me was teaching and high school teaching in a really poor neighborhood of New York City called East Harlem. I did that for five years, and that really got me into understanding and spending time with young people, and I really enjoyed that. That’s really what I love most in the world. Sometimes people talk about a happy place, and whenever I think about going to my happy place, it’s going to a room full of kids. That’s what I love. I went through a lot of different things. I had learned music early, so I became a professional musician for a while, but what I played was the classical guitar and the lute—the 16th century lute—so there was not a huge amount of demand for that, and I realized I would never earn a really good living playing that. So, at one point, I decided to go to business school, and I was fortunate to get into Harvard Business School. I went there. It was a very strange experience for somebody who had been in education and been a musician before, but I learned a lot. And what I mostly learned there was about something I now call reframing. I learned about seeing something in that case. It was companies and industries, but it could be anything from a very different perspective, and some people now refer to that as paradigms,

and it turns out that I'm very good at doing that kind of thinking and seeing things in new ways. So, what I've done recently is bring this new reframing thinking into education and into thinking about what we all do and how we bring up our young people. And the world put together a system over this last several hundred years of education, which is really what I call learning in advance. We take all our children, or as many as we can, and do this: we put them into classrooms in groups with the teacher, and we try to get them to learn various parts of our background and our history of the information that humans have accumulated over all our years of existence. And there's a lot of that information, and it takes a very long time to get even some of it into there, and that's the way we operated until basically now. We still operate that way. If you have a child, you are legally obligated to send that child to school for six years, or in some places, 12 years, or in my case, 20 years, and spend their time learning before they make any real contributions to the world in terms of accomplishing anything or adding any value. So that's our system today: learning in advance for years and years and years, and then when you finish your learning, when you finish your education, usually when you become an adult, you get to start. Unfortunately, you have to start at the very bottom because you haven't done it before. You start in some profession or job. And what I looked at was... That doesn't seem right to me. And it may have been right in terms of the fact that in a world where we couldn't get much information easily, where it wasn't available, we couldn't do much. Therefore, it made a whole lot of sense to put the young people into these classrooms and teach them things that would be helpful, like reading, writing, and math. But that doesn't make sense anymore. The time when I started to realize that things were changing was when I had my own little software company. We were making video games for corporate learning. It was called games to train, and I had a number of employees, and they were all considerably younger than me. They were typically in their late teens or early twenties, and when they had to do something, they did it in very different ways than I would do those same things. So, for example, if I didn't know something and I needed information, I would do research, I would go to the library, I would... that was the very beginning of the internet back then, but there wasn't really a whole lot that you could search for, so most of the time I would call people that I knew. And I knew people in a number of different fields, and I'd find an expert, and it would take me time, but I'd finally connect and usually get the information I needed. My employees did something very different. They took this rudimentary internet that they understood that they had been part of, and they posted their questions in various forums that already existed at that time. And guess what? They would get an answer almost immediately, and it would come from lots of different people. It would sometimes be a better answer than I would have gotten, and certainly a faster answer than I would have gotten by my old methods of asking people. So, I said, 'Oh well, that's something new!' And then the more I looked at things, the more I saw that well, this is happening in many different ways; they're not just doing their writing or creating in the same ways that I would. They're not writing essays like I learned to do. They're making videos; they're making YouTubes. I remember one of my employees telling me, 'Oh, there's this new thing called YouTube. You should check it out! I put my videos up on it!' and so I saw things were changing. In addition, I talked to a lot of parents, a lot of people who had kids, and educators who were doing this. They started having a feeling that things were different and that their young people were different in more ways than just the usual generational change, which was okay. We're going to dress a little differently. We're going to use a little different slang and language that have always happened. But now there were some bigger changes. Their kids were online, playing video games a lot of the time, spending huge amounts of their time off, and doing this kind of thing. They wanted to connect when they could, or they wanted to be on their phones, which were just emerging—their smartphones—and so I saw something. I heard something continuously from people, and they didn't have a way to name it. They just said our kids are strange. Strange things are happening, and so that's what led me to this idea—the concept that we were in a new world. We were entering this new digital world, this new digital culture. It started out as just a world of things that you could conne-

ct to, and in that world, these were people who grew up with it. They were natives. They spoke it. It had been there ever since they were born or were close to it, whereas adults like me were people who had come to this world later on in our lives. We were metaphorically immigrants in this new world. So, I wrote the piece ‘Digital natives, Digital immigrants’ and the rest is, of course, history. That’s what Gülden has just translated into Turkish after 20 years, and it was published in, I think, 2001. Let me just tell you a story, because this is a very important story. So, when I published this article, I had a friend who owned an online academic journal called “On the Horizon.” And he said, Okay, I’ll publish that article, and he did. This was just at the beginning of the internet, and online was not very big, and this was just the word I would use as obscure. It was not easy to find, and then one day I got an email. It said, Hello, we are the Gifted Children’s Association of New Zealand.

Gülden Demir: New Zealand?

Marc Prensky: New Zealand! We read your article in the newsletter of the Gifted Children’s Association of Tasmania, which is an island south of Australia and another very remote place. Can we republish? I said, Wow! Well, first, yes, of course you can republish! But what I suddenly realized is that the world was full of people who had suddenly become connected to all this information and who were searching for new ideas, and so they connected that, and I draw a straight line from there to the fact that Gülden has just translated that article 20 years later, or more than that, that people in places like Turkey are looking for new ideas and interested in hearing these things. And it’s the world that has changed a lot. We’ve gotten automatic translation in a lot of ways, but we still have people like you who are at this media literacy group who are trying to find these new ideas and communicate them to your own culture, and I think that’s beautiful!

Gülden Demir: Thank you, Marc! It was such a privilege to listen to this story. So, your articles that you mentioned were published in 2001, and just one term caught my attention that you used as a reframing. So, from this concept, I want to ask about what has changed so far. Since 2001, what about the changes that have occurred since then, like what is different today? Maybe we can think about 20th-century education and 21st-century education. What is different from 20th-century education? Can you tell us a bit more about it?

Marc Prensky: Certainly! The changes, as I think most of us know, are profound, but the interesting part is that they’re not on the surface. If I go to Istanbul, I can see the same buildings that have been there for hundreds, or in some cases, maybe even thousands of years. I can also go to the homes where we live. We go to the same buildings. We eat very similar food. So, on the surface, not much has changed, but underneath, everything has changed! The infrastructure is what has changed! So, in that time since the last 20–23 years, say, since the turn of the millennium, the world has connected. The world has connected information, so pretty much anything that ever made it to print—and even a lot that didn’t make it to print—is in video and in sound. And this is available to anybody who has a device and is connected to the internet. And that has become something like two-thirds of the people on planet Earth. While we still have work to do to connect some more people, it is really totally new that this information is available. Second, we have connected with each other! So, this is a great example of why we’re sitting here and doing this: I am now connected to people in Türkiye and other places where I never could have been connected before. I can call up people, I can connect to people, and I can do it with people I’ve already met, but I continuously meet people that I have not met before, like Hediyeullah and things like that, and that makes it go further and further. So today, if a young person says that they want to connect with somebody, they can probably figure out a way to do that. And that has huge implications, which we can talk about in a minute. Then, the third thing—and this is months old! Months old! This new AI, this ChatGPT, because what that does is connect our thinking to all that information in a much more

direct way, a different way, and in some sense, an indirect way because it does it statistically, and that’s what ChatGPT does. Just put ChatGPT—it just puts things together statistically—but in doing that, it connects all the information that it was trained on, which is the whole internet. So, if you ask a question about anything, you can ask the question, “Tell me the history of this all through humanity, and it will tell you that it isn’t perfect. You need to fact-check it like you do with people, but this is totally new! So, we’re living in a world that looks the same and tastes the same, but underneath is totally different!

Gülden Demir: So, it sounds like seeing things in a new way, maybe in a better way—in a more creative way?

Marc Prensky: Well, I would say that brings us back to reframing, and I would say that one of the things that happens with human beings is that they tend to fall into patterns of looking at things. And those patterns change over time. So, at one point, we were organized in terms of families, and then that got bigger and more organized in terms of clans and tribes, and today we often look at things in terms of nation-states. That’s a way to look at the world, and we say okay, given that we look at the world that way. Here’s what we can do, what we can’t do, what we should do, and what we can think about. But often, there are just totally different ways of thinking about the world. The same information, the same world, but we look at it differently. You know a great example is gender! So, we can say, well, we look at the world, and we have men on one side, or males, and almost all females on the other side. By the way, they have different roles and they have different things, different strands, and all this kind of stuff, and that’s the way it is. Or we can reframe and say no! You know they both have different reproductive functions, but there’s no reason necessarily to see them as different. And that’s just a totally reframing we’re going through in so many ways in the world. We’re going through that with LGBTQ. We’re going through that with what you can—you know, drugs you can take, whether marijuana is a good legal drug or an illegal drug. We’re going through a lot of reframing. And once you see the world in a new way, it’s very hard to go back to the old way. You may accept it, you may not accept it, but you now see the world in two ways, and it’s very much like the optical illusions that we all know where you can see either two faces facing each other or you can see a jug depending on whether you’re looking at the white or the black. Once you see both, you can’t see them both at once. It’s very hard, but you can switch back and forth really easily, and you can’t go back! So, that’s what’s really going on now. I think the business, the struggle, or the effort that we’re all in together is trying to take people who see things only one way for very good reasons because they grew up thinking the world was that way. Their world was that way, and we’re trying to show them that they can look at the world in a different way. If they do that, it has different implications for what they will do, what they will say, how they will live, etc. There are many huge implications. So that’s really what we’re doing here. That’s what you guys are doing with your journal. That’s what we are all trying to say: ‘Well, you don’t have to agree with us, but listen up because there’s another way to look at this!’

Gülden Demir: Thank you, Marc! You highlighted some significant differences here, so I’d like to move on to another specific question, but I must say... I was born in 1987. I’ve been teaching with experience for more than 15 years, so I’m a kind of digital immigrant. It’s fine to figure out what’s going on in the New World in this new digital age, struggling with things, and trying to learn some new ways to understand the language of our students. I’d like to ask you this specific question because it’s a kind of handicap for young people: What labels are given to young people by adults? Because they experienced the world before them. What about the labels given to young people by adults, parents, teachers, and educators? What is young people’s handicap here?

Marc Prensky: I like that question! Labeling is something that humans do. It’s very important; in fact, most education is really about nomenclature. It’s really about giving different names to pheno-

mena that we see in the world so that we can talk about them and distinguish them. So, there’s nothing wrong with putting labels on things except when that label makes assumptions or carries assumptions that are not valid. So, the one thing that has been relatively constant over a very long period of human history is that change has been slow, and there has always been change and new things happening. We invented fire, we tamed animals, we got agriculture, and we got everything. We got printing and many other things that we got over time, but it all came very slowly. The expectation was that things would, more or less, remain the same from generation to generation. If you were a young person, you would grow up and fill a role that already existed somewhere in the world when that person got old and passed away. So, we would have whatever they are—everything from doctors to teachers to parents—we think it was a replacement. It was a world of replacement because we had finite lives; we had to replace ourselves, and so what was the goal of the adults? Well, they wanted to be well replaced. They said our young people should grow up to be people like us because, look at how good we were! We did really well, so they should be people like us! I used to call them little uses, and that’s what we did, and that’s why we put them through all the school and training. And you know that started way back when parents and masters would train some kids to do the family business, to make something, or to do this. Well, that started to change when this digital world started appearing because it was moving so much faster; it was moving at a speed where something that was true, good, or the best one year could totally disappear. The next year, and I don’t know if any of you remember the thing called the Blackberry, which at one point was the greatest device in the world, suddenly something else came out that was better like the iPhone or the smartphone, and it was, you know, disappeared. So, the change—the pace of change—started increasing incredibly rapidly, and Ray Kurzweil and others talk about the exponential curve and how if you were to put coins on a chessboard, for example, and just double one coin on the first square, two coins, four coins, eight coins, sixteen coins... You start out with not that many coins, but by the end of the board, you have more coins than there are things in the world. You have this enormous number, and that’s called exponential growth. One example is doubling every period. So, that’s what started happening in so many ways that we started seeing it in computer chips and Moore’s Law, and things started changing a lot more rapidly, which meant that things that were very important to a generation might not be as important to the next generation! And one of the great examples for me as a father was watching my son grow up and teaching him something that I had learned: when you meet somebody new, you look them in the eye and you shake their hand, and he didn’t want to do that. And he still doesn’t do that unless he’s forced, he understands, or I tell him in advance. He doesn’t look people in the eye. He looks at people on the screen mostly, and so things change that were very important at one point... changed when it comes to the next thing. Now that it means we have to bring up our kids in the world that they’re going to live in, If they were going to live in our world essentially with a few modifications and changes—you know, maybe even cars instead of horses—we could deal with that; it was a slow change. Now that they are living, they are already starting to live in a world where change is much faster than humans are used to or comfortable with, and humans don’t really enjoy changing. They’re very adaptable. There is an interesting paradox because humans are very adaptable, but changing something that you’ve done for a long time, that you feel is part of you, or something you like is very hard, and it typically only happens when you’re pushed, when you feel a crisis when something is going on that makes you want to change. One of the words we use for that is comfort zone. People have a comfort zone. It’s hard to get them to move out of their comfort zone many times. So that’s what’s happening with regard to education, in my view. We have been very comfortable for a very long time, or at least 100 maybe a couple hundred years, with a system that says, ‘Okay! If you want your kids to be like you and you want them to be slightly better, maybe rise a little higher in the hierarchy. Yes, send them to school. You teach them what we know as humans about organization, about writing, about how the world is, about geography, about math, about all these kinds of things, because if they do well in

that, that will make them humans like us!’ Worthy of replacing us, advancing our civilization perhaps slightly... And that worked. I don’t think that works anymore. I think that is the huge change because the world, and again, it’s not the world on the surface; it’s the world underneath, will be so different in the period—even today, but certainly—in the next 50 hundred years, which is when these kids in school today are going to live, the world will be so different that the old methods of preparing them are almost useless. And they are feeling it because there are so many young people in the world who are just disaffected—there’s much stronger words than that—disaffected with school and say this just doesn’t apply to me. Why am I here? And the reason you’re here is actually because of three big reasons. One is that you’re legally required to be here. Two is that your parents need a place to put you so that they know you’re safe while they go off and work, and the third is that employers—this is called signaling—so, when you actually finish this and go look for a job, your employer will know that you can actually do something that is a little bit complex, but more importantly, that you can do things that you don’t want to do but they want you to do. That is the biggest signal of education, and most of education is not stuff we want to do yet. I hope that will change. It’s stuff we don’t want to do but we’re told to do, and we do it, and we’re rewarded with grades, smiles, pats on the head, or whatever we’re rewarded with, but that’s indoctrination into how culture works.

Gülden Demir: I think it was important to underline the assumptions of the adults. They experienced the world before us, offering some frames and some guidelines on how to live in it. And young people and children are resisting, like not accepting their stock of knowledge because they experience something new. We know that, and also what I understood from your example, Sky saying no, we know that this digital age has changed the way people communicate. They have been experiencing something new, and I want to ask my question here on the future relationship between teacher and students, parents and children, especially in this context of intergenerational communication. What would you say?

Marc Prensky: It’s really important because people are struggling with it, and it’s something that is worldwide. You hear the same things, the same arguments, and the same complaints everywhere you go, everywhere I go, and I go to a lot of places. Right, I used to go to eat more, but now I still go to places that I haven’t been, and I hear the same struggles. The struggle is that we think these particular sets of things are important. They’re important for our culture. They’re important because you’re growing up and being successful, which is what parents want for their kids. They’re important for the continuation of society as we know it and like it. And that’s the important thing we like. So, we want that to continue. In order to do that, we have always controlled young people in many ways, and we’ve—it’s the technical term for that is enculturation—we, parents, teach the rules of the culture to their little kids: you do this, you don’t do this, you take off your shoes, you don’t take off your shoes, you do this in public, you don’t do that in public... Those rules... Then religion teaches another set of rules: you need to do this on these days, you need to not do this on these days, you need to behave and say certain kinds of things... And finally, school is really there to control people by teaching them all the rules that they have to follow and the things they should do. So, it’s really been a system of control, but it was a system in a sense that paid off. It was a system that said, ‘Well, if you follow these rules, you might actually become president of Turkey, or you might actually become, you know what you want to be, an academician, or all these kinds of things because that’s the path.’ That is so different now, and the thing that’s interesting is that none of us really know the exact path. It used to be okay; the adults knew the path. They had been through this path. They’d been on it. They’d seen the pitfalls. They’ve seen what happens if you don’t study hard, don’t go to school every day, or don’t do this, and they’ve seen the charges that say, ‘Well, if you do go to school for so many years, your income is likely statistically to be a million dollars higher!’ or whatever it is! We all knew that stuff—that’s not true anymore, necessarily. So, the young people feel this. I think instinctively. I don’t know the right word to use, but

they understand it just in the same way that my son, Sky—again, I’m going to talk about something I know—who just graduated from literally high school ranked number one academically in California for public schools. It’s number one. Everybody knows that if you mention the name of his high school, you know it’s worth something. It’s number one. He hated! He thought it was just totally irrelevant, with a few exceptions, but mostly he never wants to set foot back there. And what they did mostly was stress them out. What they did mostly was say, ‘Well, if you don’t do this stuff, we won’t give you the grades, and there you won’t get into the right college, and you won’t have the right life that you want to have!’ Well, he will decide it on his own. More and more young people are figuring out that they have to forge a new path in this new world! And the most interesting part of this is that we’ve just entered, and this is exciting because just when we were kind of thinking, well, I don’t know, are we really immigrants; do older people know a little bit about technology and younger people don’t know enough and whatever? We suddenly didn’t get this AI. And here, we’re all immigrants. Everybody’s an immigrant because it hasn’t existed, and you know it’s only technology if it was created after you were born, and we were all born before the technology showed up. It’s technology. It’s new. It’s a new world, and we’re all struggling with how to do it, what we do with it, what’s good, what’s bad, and what’s good about it. Where does it help with the things we used to do? Where does it help us do new things? And that is a huge opportunity for just what we’re talking about for generations to work together because it or it should be at least theoretically. Because ideally, well, people who have lived a life have learned a set of things they’ve said; they have some thinking about whether, if you do this, this will happen. They’ve learned about some consequences. Some of those are probably still true. Many of them. Some of them are not. So, what we have to now recalibrate is what the consequences of different kinds of actions are. That’s the big recalibration that has to go on in humanity, and if you go on and take the adults alone, they will tell you because they know what the consequences are of every little thing you do. We’ve had so much experience. The young people, of course, know nothing about it because they haven’t done very much, but they’re starting to see if they can do this, say with a tool they have. You know, young people like my son began using ChatGPT in school the very first day it appeared, and the consequences—you know, they have discovered the consequences. Sometimes you get away with it if you do this or that; sometimes they, you know, hold you by the collar and tell your plagiarizing. They’re starting to figure out what those consequences are of living in the world with the affordances of the things they now have. And it would be nice if we did that together without judgment. That’s a very hard thing to do. That’s why we’re struggling because there’s a lot of judgment from people who claim they have experience, and they do have experience, of course! If you’ve lived for—you know—80 years, you have 80 years of experience. Is it a relevant experience? Where is the relevant experience? It may be relevant experience in experiencing how your body changes as you age, yes, but it may not be relevant experience to figure out what’s the best way to find something out, get something done, connect with other people, or do this. So, again, I think that’s a great word, and I haven’t ever used it before, but I think it’s really important that we are recalibrating. We are just recalibrating, and specifically, what we are recalibrating are the effects of our actions.

Gülден Demir: Thank you so much, Marc. It seems like, unfortunately, we have some problems. Still, individual differences are not taken into consideration, and the teachers are using the same language—maybe not updated prompts they bring in when they go into the class. And it seems like most of the teachers are still struggling with this digital world. The new tools, I mean. So, I want to ask about your recommendation. What would you suggest us—parents, teachers, and educators—to use these significant differences to our advantage? What should we do? Marc Prensky: Thank you for asking that. I think it’s really important that we figure it out. I have always thought that the most important thing to do is to watch and listen, and that is something we’re not particularly good at with our own children and with our own students. We think we know the answers, so why should we watch them

struggle like we did, etc.? But unless you watch and listen carefully, you will never know the changes are taking place and you will never know how to address them. But it's a struggle. I struggle with this every day. My son tells me I give him lectures, which I do, and he said you know you should listen more, and I have to every day. I said, 'Well, okay,' I'm going to really try to do that, and what we're listening for is what are their goals, what do they want, and do we think those are good? Do we want to help them reach those goals? Hopefully, in many cases, we do, and if we do, what are the best ways to do that? For example, one of the things that often gets asked of kids—at least in my part of the world—is that you meet a new, you know, the kid of somebody you know, and you say, 'Oh, hi! What's your favorite subject in school?' That's five choices! That's like a five-choice, multiple-choice test! No! They might not be interested in any of that stuff! The amount of things that you can be interested in in the world might be billions. So, why should we limit them to five? And we have to learn to listen in a more nuanced way and ask the questions that bring out this stuff. For example, when I used to ask kids, Well, suddenly passion became a big deal in the world—what's your passion? Follow your passion! And so we would ask, and the teachers would ask the kids, What's your passion? They would say, I don't know. And what do you do? When they say I don't know, well, you have to follow up! What do you watch on YouTube? What do you do? What would you do with your free time if you had nothing to do? You know, and if it's sleep, okay, but that's maybe what you're interested in right now because you're too stressed out to do anything else. We have to be much more open to a variety of things, and I put things into three categories when I talk to young people. I say, well, here's three things that I can help you with. Do you want to realize a dream? Do you have a dream where you say gee, I would really love to see this? I think we can desalinate water, I think we can bring people together, I think we can do... Okay! Let's do! So, we can focus on helping you realize your dream. The second thing is, are there problems you see that you care about? And every single young person sees. They just have to walk out their door or wake up and not even walk out the door, and they see tons of problems, some of which they'll care about and some of which they won't care about. And so which ones do you care about? Okay, we can work on fixing them, and then the third one is: who do you want to help? So, most people have a group of people—it could be their family, it could be their religion, it could be anything they want to help. Some people want to help people who are not humans, like animals, right? I call them people who are not beings and who are not humans, like animals. So, once you start probing in those ways, you start understanding who they are as individuals and then how to help them. And there's a new thing that a friend of mine has been talking about that I think is really important here that has come into the world, and that's called affinity groups. It's a little bit of a technical term, but it means we used to have communities. First, they were based on where you lived, and they're still communities based on where you live. And then they got a little broader. They were basically on a religion for certain things that you shared, such as a community, etc. But now there are these things—affinity groups—that say, What are you interested in? What do you care about that? I don't care who you are, what you look like, where you live in the world, or what your age is. If you and I are both interested in the same thing, we can share something about that. We can learn from each other. We can work together. We don't have to say, 'Are you a member of my group or not?' You know, I can't work with you because you don't share my nationality, or you don't share my religion, or you don't share my philosophy. We can leave all that stuff out and just say, Are we interested in the same thing? Do we have infinity? Are we an affinity group? The wonderful line from my friend who talks about this stuff says that with the internet, everybody can now find the group in the world in which they are in the top ten percent. So, nobody has to be at the bottom. They can. There's some group of people who have similar interests in which they know more than other people or are better at something than other people, and that's a very positive thing. I think the huge opportunity is to connect across generations in affinity groups, and this is happening. It's certainly happening in the game's world. That's kind of where this whole thing got started, because adults played

games. Young people played games, and it happened on the internet! Because, as the old joke says on the internet, nobody knows if you're a dog, right? You can be... Nobody knows anything except what comes out of the internet about you, and that has good and bad. I mean, you can fake things. You can fool people, and you can do it in negative ways, but mostly it has so many huge positive things that that's where we should put a lot of our focus. So, a couple of other things that I thought: adults—if you're like me, if you're not like me, if you like to teach right, and probably in this group we like to teach—if somebody or my son asks me a question, I'll give him a lecture for as long as I—you know—can go on until he'll stop me. It's something that a lot of humans have. We like to teach! The trouble with that is how we run our education system. We run it through teaching. Direct instruction! We put a group of people in front of us, or at best, one to one, and we teach them. Well, direct instruction is great! It works, but it only works if the people being instructed ask for that instruction if they want that instruction! If you say, 'Look! I want to ride a bike. Teach me how to ride a bike.' Then you're going to pay attention, but if you're a parent and say, 'You know you're a kid and you need to learn to ride a bike.' and just like happened with my kid in swimming, I found out years later that he hated the swimming lessons he took. He did them, and I forced him to do them. It's good that he knows how to swim. He'll be a safer person in the water, but that instruction was not well received or happily received. So, if we're going to teach people, we really need to help them reach their goals, and that really makes us much more coaches, mentors, advisors, and then teachers. When you're a teacher, what's your curriculum? Okay, let's get it out there into their heads. People don't necessarily want it in their heads, and that's a real issue that education is struggling with now. It's a real huge generation that we have a huge worldwide system of educators who are very good in many cases at putting things into kids' heads in teaching, and they'll tell you all the best. We have some great teachers! Well, that means zero if the people don't want to learn the stuff. But then there's an even little problem, because why? How do we...? We have all these discussions in education about motivation and how we motivate our kids to learn this stuff. And there's only one way, and that is for them to have something that they want to accomplish for which this information or skill is useful. They have to realize that! So, which leads me to say it: we made a mistake for good reasons, but we made a mistake in making our education our system for bringing up people about teaching and learning. And don't tell that to educators because that's their whole lives, but that is a mistake! What we should do is based on accomplishment, and teaching and learning should be a byproduct of that. When you need it, you get it, but that shouldn't be the goal. If you go to almost any academic institution or school in the world today, they'll tell you their job is learning, or teaching and learning in some cases, but they all talk about learning. Our lifelong learning... How do we learn? What's the best way to learn? Do we forget our learning over the summer? It all becomes about learning. Well, no, it doesn't! I don't think that's going to help much in the future because it's all there. You can learn it right in your pocket when you need it. So I try to build this world, hopefully bringing up young people on real-world accomplishments, on realizing dreams, on fixing problems, on helping other people, and hopefully we'll get there.

GülDen Demir: I hope so. Marc, it seems like—you know—connecting with young people and children is not enough to have a broad understanding of their perspective and their experiences. I think we have to change the language that we use, and we need to try some creative ideas like those you have just offered us. Thank you so much for this.

Marc, we would like to thank you again for being with us despite time zone differences because, as you know, Istanbul is 10 hours ahead of California. I must say you are ahead of your time! So, thank you for accepting our invitation and for the audience's questions and attention. I must say, please keep an eye out for more communications from the Journal of Media Literacy Studies team. You can watch the recording of this session on YouTube, so thank you to everyone.

Marc Prensky: Thank you.